
**IMPACT OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY ON COLLECTION
DEVELOPMENT IN LIBRARIES OF HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM**

Anjali S. Kadappa¹ & Dr. Yuvraj G. Jadhav²

¹Ph. D. Scholar, Shivaji University, Kolhapur

²Assistant Prof., Dept. of LIS, Shivaji University, Kolhapur

Corresponding Author - Anjali S. Kadappa

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Abstract:

Information technology and the Internet bring many opportunities and challenges for library professionals. Due to the impact of ICT, most libraries started sharing resources in different ways. Nowadays, the use of E-resources is increasing in the higher education system as a tool for teaching-learning and research. It is also a supporting pillar of higher education in fulfilling educational objectives. Teachers, researchers and the users of libraries of higher education systems are involved in the subscription of E-resources from various publishers, vendors, aggregators and different consortia, which can make complex in collection development. E-resources are also based on collection development policy. The libraries should have a collection development policy for the smooth functioning of the library. The paper focuses on the basic concept of E-resources, types of E-resources, and Collection Development. Collection development policy and use of E-resources in Higher Education system etc.

Keywords: *Collection development, Collection development Policy, Information Technology, E-resources, Higher Education etc.*

Introduction:

Over the last five decades, the higher education system has grown exponentially to meet all the demands of quality education. The growth of higher education presents a very impressive picture. E-Resources have become an inseparable part of the education system. Over the past few years, many techniques and related standards have been developed, allowing documents to be created and distributed in electric form. Nowadays, libraries are shifting towards new media such as E-Resources for their collection development which is better fulfilled by the demands of the user. A significant transformation has been noticed

in collection development policies and practices due to the impact of information technology.

An electronic source is any information source that the library provides access in electronic format, including full-text journals, newspapers, company information, e-books, digital image, dictionaries, encyclopaedias, electronic data, market research, career information etc.

The library of any discipline performs three major tasks. i.e. acquiring the proper document, preserving it and providing access to it. The processing period for these tasks is now significantly

less due to the ICT role, making it possible within a short period.

Collection Development:

“A collection development is a process which permits the library to develop a collection of materials responding to the information needs and service requirements of the users. It is defined as "a process that allows the identification of the strengths and weaknesses of the documents collection of a library in terms of the needs of the users and the resources of the community.”

It is also known as the process of systematic planning and building a useful and balanced collection of library materials over time within a set budget, based on assessed ongoing information needs of the library users in a timely and economical manner using different information resources locally held as well as from other organizations. Collection development includes:

- The formulation of selection criteria.
- Planning for resource sharing and replacement of lost and damaged items.
- Routine selection and de-selection decisions.

Collection development is an important concept for extension in higher education and library research activities. Using ICTs helps save time in collection development, promotes quick delivery of information materials and enhances communication with publishers and book vendors.

Collection Development Policy:

“Planning is essential in collection development, and framing a written collection development policy is the first step in the planning process. Collection Development Policy is a formal written

statement of the principles guiding a library’s selection of materials, including the criteria used in making the selection and de-selection decisions and policies concerning gifts and exchange” (Reitz, 2004).

E-Resources collection development policy, should include a general statement, the scope of the policy, e-Resources to be collected, selection criteria for fee-based, selection responsibilities, acquisition process and procedure for evaluation and license.

Purpose of Collection Development Policy:

The purpose of a collection development policy is to create a collection of library materials that supports the library's mission. All the kinds of materials to be collected or accessed should be made with the mission statement in mind. As libraries acquire more and more electronic resources, guidelines concerning selecting and developing these resources should also be incorporated into the policy.

Impact of ICT on library Collection development:

Library collection goes beyond the print materials and includes the CDs/DVDs, audio and video cassettes, e-books e-journals and e-databases. Earlier traditional paper as a storage medium which is now a days replaced with electronic media. The online public access catalogue has also changed the traditional card catalogue. The internet, online journal services, and e-mail services have provided a helping hand to library users for providing comprehensive information on their respective subjects.

ICT’s are used in all areas of collection development activity like

selection, acquisition, evaluation, co-operative efforts etc. Selection can be done by making use of online publisher's catalogues, online book reviews, online sites, faculty-librarian communication for providing online suggestions and recommendations and online alert services. ICT used in acquisition work of pre-ordering and ordering process and also communication with vendors. It is also used in evaluation process to measure circulation statistics, provide budget reports, e-resources usage, online user survey etc. Transaction log analysis of E-Resources provides information on the use of electronic journals and databases.

The collection development process includes analysis of the users' needs and ensuring that it is served adequately towards meeting the needs of the users.

ICT's practical impact is on the collection development process like acquisition, ordering, bill payment, accessioning, cataloguing, and OPAC system. It can be used as a gateway for accessing information in libraries as they provide facilities to browse, search and locate information. The web OPAC can help to realize the resource-sharing activity among libraries. A union catalogue is also essential for document selection in collection development.

E-Resources:

E-Resource refers to all the products a library provides through a computer network. They are also known as online information resources covering the materials in digital format accessible electronically. These are valuable tools for teaching-learning and research. It is the supporting pillar of higher education in fulfilling educational objectives. Access to the databases is free of cost of some portals by publishers and vendors, and

others require a subscription for such databases. By subscribing to the databases, the researcher gets access to thousands of scholarly articles in the field of specialization or research. Users can access via VPN or Proxy server to enter the Institution's IP range which will automatically recognize and grant access to the content their institution has purchased. The most common tool used to provide this service is EZProxy. Higher education libraries can also subscribe through different consortia due to fund shortages.

Examples of e-Resources are electronic journals (e-Journal), electronic books (e-Books), and online databases in varied digital formats, Search engines for full text books, Adobe Acrobat documents (.pdf), WebPages (.htm, .html, .asp etc.) and more.

Impact of E-resources and services on higher education and research:

In the 21st Century, Information Technology has brought rapid changes to education. Conventional teaching and learning are gradually moving towards online. Nowadays, the concept of a digital library, virtual library and electronic libraries have arrived. Electronic resources have many advantages over traditional information resources. For teaching and learning, electronic resources are available in web-enabled mediums. There are a lot of developments witnessed in recent years in e-publishing. Publishers are interested in issues like publishing costs, changing leadership, changing user expectations, rights management and archiving. Many Authors and corporate bodies expect their self-publishing of scholarly publications and quality assurance. Researchers are interested in accessing full-text journals

and reference linking in complex information spaces.

E-Resources and information technology have brought rapid changes to the higher education system in India. Websites and internet services are essential for accessing e-Resources in education and research. E-Resources have a prominent role to play in supporting higher education and in achieving the goal of objectives in higher education. E-Resources are rich sources for getting information for those students who want extra learning material in addition to their regular classroom activities. i.e. in their research activity.

The advent of computer, software, internet technologies etc. have shaken the existing concept of the profession. With such changes, the structure and nature of library profession has also changed in a dynamic way. The library and information professionals experience stress as they readjust their lives with the changing library environment, job structure, job promotion etc. (Salunke&Hemade, 2015)

Many studies show the use of E-Resources in different fields of higher education, such as Medical Education, Engineering Education, and College education. The effect of the use of technology is on students' academic performance and efficacy. Mostly, E-Resources use can have a positive impact on student's performance if it is used properly. E-Resources are helpful for education in many ways. In the information technology era, most higher education institutions started subscribing to e-resources to meet user demands and expectations.

UGC-Based E-resources for Higher Education:

Learning-ICT initiatives of MHRD and UGC listed some e-resources that the

research community from higher education can use and benefit from them. These E-resources are:

- SWAYAM
- UG/PG Moocs
- E-PG Pathshala
- E-content courseware in UG subjects
- SWAYAMPURABHA
- CEC-UGC Youtube Channel
- National Digital Library (NDL)
- Shodhganga
- E-shadhsindhu
- Vidwan
- NPTEL

The above resources cover a wide range of subjects useful to academic users of higher education and the research community.

Due to the ICT, users from all over the world are attached with the help of web-based library services. The efficient and essential benefit for the user is that they can access resources at a time from anywhere.

Challenges Faced with E-Resources in higher education:

- Shortage of funds
- Technical infrastructure
- Lack of professional Skill.
- Privacy
- Control of E-Resources
- Limited Access to computer demand

Advantages of E-Resources in Higher education System:

- It helps to eliminates printing binding and postage cost.
- It helps in space management i.e. less space needed for E-Resources.
- Integration/Alignment of different media like image, sound, video can be done at an ease.

- Low cost of production as compared to print document.
- Allows user in remote accession of documents from anywhere at any time.
- Manipulation of data at regular interval and whenever needed and can be kept up-to-date by time-to-time.
- It can facilitate in easy duplication of document.

Disadvantages:

- All E-Resources devices require power, if there is a break-down of power then it will be difficult to access the E-Resources.
- Cost of Infrastructure is very high.
- Always need special equipment for access.
- Hardware and Software compatibility problem may occur.
- Problem of various kinds of physical barrier.
- Copyright valuation problem takes place.
- Use of product according to user convenience is not possible every time. Sometimes there are some technical restrictions.

Conclusion:

Collection development is a continuous process at any organization, so we have to check the utility of items and subscription costs carefully. The collection development policy guides library professionals in making decisions regarding E-Resources purchases. Nowadays, the demand from users of higher education for E-Resources is increasing. Information and technology made it easy and simple to access the E-Resources in various disciplines of the higher education system to meet the user demands.

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